

Technological training in higher education,
lessons and recommendations

Abdelhammid Bourouaha

Associate professor at Bejaia University – Algeria

Mecas laboratory, Tlemcen University

Email: b.abdelhammid@gmail.com

Abstract:

Technology has become commonplace entity in all aspects of life. Across the past fifty years, the use of the technology has fundamentally changed the practices and procedures of nearly all forms of endeavour within business, governance, industry, communication ..etc. Within education, technology has begun to have a presence but the effect has not been as extensive as in other fields. However, following the continuous changes of the worlds and the appearance all of internet, digitalization, smarts technology, social media, there is a huge change in education. Nowadays, technology is becoming the first source that enhance learning and training following its relation to internet, and it is developed by them. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to highlight, at first, the importance of education, training, learning and technology. Second, the paper demonstrates the relationship between all of the previous factors and their effect on higher education through teacher technology training.

Keywords: training, technology, learning, teacher technology training.

ملخص:

أصبحت التكنولوجيا كياناً مألوفاً في جميع جوانب الحياة. على مدار الخمسين عاماً الماضية، أدى استخدام التكنولوجيا إلى تغيير ممارسات وإجراءات جميع أشكال المساعي تقريباً في مجال الأعمال والحكومة والصناعة والاتصالات ... إلخ. في مجال التعليم، بدأت التكنولوجيا في الظهور ولكن التأثير لم يكن واسع النطاق كما هو الحال في المجالات الأخرى. ومع ذلك، بعد التغييرات المستمرة للعالم وظهور كل الإنترنت، والرقمنة، وتكنولوجيا الذكاء، ووسائل التواصل الاجتماعي، هناك تغيير كبير في التعليم. في الوقت الحاضر، أصبحت التكنولوجيا هي المصدر الأول الذي يعزز التعلم والتدريب بفضل علاقتها بالإنترنت، ويتم تطويرها من قبلهم. لذلك، فإن الغرض من هذه الورقة هو تسليط الضوء، في البداية، على أهمية التعليم والتدريب والتعلم والتكنولوجيا. ثانياً، توضح الورقة العلاقة بين جميع العوامل السابقة وتأثيرها على التعليم العالي من خلال التدريب التكنولوجي للمعلمين.

الكلمات المفتاحية: التدريب، التكنولوجيا، التعلم، التدريب التكنولوجي، المعلمين.

Introduction:

Starting from the actual health situation, the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is a human social and economic crisis that has attacked the core of human existence (Verma & Gustafsson, 2020, p. 253). At least 316 million people in 42 states have been asked to stay at home to slow down the pandemic (Kim, 2020). In this aspect, different states have been susceptible to make substantial transformations where the workplace operations of many businesses went virtual using high technologies. From another side, it is so necessary to look for new methods to follow the studies and education where Higher education is also changing following the changes in all the sectors (Royce Ann Collins, 2014, p. 221)

The fastest changes of the world, the essential role of technology in all domains and sectors, the appearance of new fields following technology, the technological penetration in all fields, the impossibility to live without technology (starting from the idea of facilitating the life with technology and we arrive to the result of where we could say that technology changes our genetics, Technology remains nowadays as the air of the growth and development process because it facilitates the process of transformation from traditional to developed process. With the arrive of technology in our homes, there is a great expectation that new instructional technologies would revolutionize teaching and learning in American higher education in special and all the world in general (Geoghegan, 1994; Gilbert, 1994).

With the high spread of technology, the majority of today's students come to class armed with smartphones, laptops and iPods. It refers that This era of pervasive technology has significant implications for our lives in global and for higher education in special. In addition, student demographics around the world are changing significantly and these changes are dictating the need for colleges and universities to balance resources with sound and efficient pedagogical practices (Layne & Lake, 2014, p. 3).

Some researchers argue that new technologies are revolutionizing teaching and learning (Anderson & Whitelock, 2004; Dey et al., 2009; Stover, 2007). From the other side, other researchers suggest that the integration of technology in the curriculum is leading to the demise of education, as we know it (Ferreira, 2012). However, other researchers maintain that the digital environments created by these technologies offer instructors an exciting opportunity to experiment with different modes of teaching and

learning in ways that cannot be replicated in a conventional learning environment (Beydoun et al., 2007).

Using technological tools At both our home and institutions, Elon University in the United States and Sheffield Hallam University in the United Kingdom, the student bodies have certainly become more international (Layne & Lake, 2014, p. 3). This latest means that Technology and communication foster the information spill over around the world. As we know, different states are using high-technology to evaluate the student's languages such as French (using TCF) and English (using IELTS or TOEFL) that are as a software's

Generally, one of the ironies of higher education is that while institutions strive to teach students to think critically and innovatively, they often seem guilty of being slow innovators in comparison to other industries, especially those sectors that hire many of our graduates, and When it comes to meeting students' changing expectations and maximizing the use of resources to impact their learning, higher education appears to lag behind its corporate, technological, media and other competitors and allies. (Prudence Layne, 2014, p. 27). Inevitably, when some institutions take the plunge and experiment with new trends in higher education, the others are watching, waiting and learning the best ways to craft their strategies and goals (Prudence Layne, 2014, p. 27).

In their article "(Re)-envisioning Classroom Design with Light and Color," Johnson and Rutler examine the relationship between classroom design, student achievement and behavior (Ruiter & Johnson, 2003). They concluded that "the teacher could cause measurable changes to student

learning behaviour and achievement by altering the classroom environment” (Prudence Layne, 2014, p. 27). To survive, it is necessary to follow the steps of the first ones such as organization, firms, administrations, universities or even firms. There for, it is necessary for our universities to follow the steps of the ones in the developed countries to get their results.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to understand all of learning, training and technology in the first step, and to understand the links between them and what are the results or recommendation to develop all of them.

This paper is organized as follows:

In the Next section, we try to highlight the theoretical side of learning following its necessity. Next, I try to give clear overview about the training the next section focused on all of technology, information and communication technologies, technology training, for education and the teacher technology training as a process to develop higher education. In addition, to that, this section has a side of different innovations in higher education such as artificial intelligence. In the last of this paper, I mention some challenges face the higher education in Algeria

And finally, the paper is concluded with a conclusion and some recommendation that help to foster higher education in Algeria.

Learning:

Dr Johnson acknowledges. “There are many people who desire certification or degree programmes who simply cannot attend a residential programme, be they single mothers, working professionals or non-traditional students. It’s part of our public mission to reach those people, and we see e-learning as a vital tool in making that possible.” (The Economist, 2008, p. 9)

Definition:

Mayer (2004) emphasises that “learning may be best supported by methods of instruction that involve cognitive activity rather than behavioural activity”. From another side, accelerated, intensive and immersion learning are educational delivery methods that have been bandied about, experimented with, criticized and hailed as new, useful, useless or destructive, depending on one’s point of view (John T. Baun, 2014, p. 13). The accelerated learning method is defined as a course that is delivered in a shorted time than normal (Brookfield, 2003; N. Lee & Horsfall, 2010).

Ways of learning:

There are different ways of learning, the most important of them are cited below:

Learning by doing:

This form of learning is very important for the firm to improve their growth and innovative capability (Gatignon & Xuereb, 1997; Germain, 1996; Koberg et al., 2003; Tether, 2002). Following (Amara et al., 2008), the firms become more efficient as they get more practice at doing what they do.

Learning by training:

The investment in the staff training pool the knowledge in the firms to develop innovations, whether it is incremental or radical innovation (Darroch & McNaughton, 2002; Freel, 2005; Romijn & Albaladejo, 2002; Subramaniam & Youndt, 2005).

Learning by interaction:

In addition to these three forms of learning, there are other forms of learning capabilities to innovation successfully following the researches of (Freeman, 1995, 1995; Wes Cohen, 1995):

Learning by searching:

Learning by searching is associated with the internal R&D activities according to the studies of (Inzelt, 1996; J. Lee, 1995; Romijn & Albaladejo, 2002). This latest (R&D activities) are necessary to create the new knowledge required to develop innovations.

Learning by using:

According to the studies of (Chandy & Tellis, 1998; Gatignon & Xuereb, 1997; Rosenberg, 1982) Using advanced technologies boost learning. Some of these technologies codified knowledge which creates new opportunities for experimentation and problem solving (Wuyts et al., 2004).

Learning by exporting:

Following the research of (Massimiliano Brat & Giulia Felice, 2012), the elements of the firm environment help the firms to learn from the market and to innovate.

Types of learning:

After mentioning the different ways of learning, it is necessary to know the different types of learning:

Active learning:

It is defined as “any instructional method that engages students in the learning process”. It requires students to do meaningful learning activities and think about what they are doing” (Prince, 2004, p. 223).

The key to active learning is that learning activity is taking place within the student's brain. This may be difficult to observe and thus noting that students are active in their behaviour may not be a true representation of whether they are 'actively' learning.

Active learning can be designed into a course irrespective of the mode of delivery. It may require a more innovative and creative approach compared to more conventional and passive forms of education.

Also, the engagement of the student through active learning, and the utilization of active learning techniques, is a critical component of a concentrated course (N. Lee & Horsfall, 2010; Scott, 2003).

Passive learning:

In the passive learning, students do not actively engage in the learning process, but they may absorb some of the information being presented. Examples of passive learning include attending a lecture, reading a paper, or watching a video. All of these activities can become a more active experience for the student but they can also be very passive activities requiring little interaction from the student (Strachan & Liyanage, 2014, p. 256).

Learning development:

Following the study (Hilsdon, 2010), learning development is defined as "a complex set of multi-disciplinary and cross-disciplinary academic roles and functions, involving teaching, tutoring, research, and the design and production of learning materials, as well as involvement in staff development, policy-making and other consultative activities".

There are different ways to develop learning such as training teachers, enhancing the courses with new tools, changing learning processes and methods at school or at the university.

Blended and hybrid courses:

From the learning methods that have transformative potential in higher education are blended courses and hybrid courses (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004)

Blended learning courses:

Blended learning is a significant departure from traditional face to face and distant learning models, because it requires a reconceptualization and reorganization of pedagogical strategies(Garrison & Kanuka, 2004, p. 97). Also, the blended courses are courses that utilise both traditional methods in teaching using digital or computer techniques (Georgina, 2007).

Blended learning is an effective and low-risk strategy which positions universities for the onslaught of technological developments that will be forthcoming in the next few years (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004, p. 96).Following the study of (Garnham & Kaleta, 2006), the blended courses:

Allow the accomplishment of learning objectives more successfully than traditional courses,

Increase interaction and contact student to student and student to instructor,

Provide more flexibility for instructor,

Accommodate more student learning than traditional courses.

Hybrid learning courses:

(Garnham & Kaleta, 2006) study defines hybrid courses as “courses in which a significant portion of the learning activities have been moved online, and time spent in the traditional classroom is reduced but not eliminated”.According to (Olapiriyakul & Scher, 2006), the three main technological components required for hybrid courses are:

Technology infrastructure,
Instruction technology,
Technology in learning.

To implement Hybrid courses, is it necessary following the study of (Olapiriyakul & Scher, 2006, p. 297-300)to develop and design web-based learning hybrid courses that includes: five main phases that are:

Course content design,
Course development,
Course implementation,
Course evaluation,
Course revision
Training:

As it mentioned in the ways of learning, learning by training remains one of the important ways to get knowledge and information. This part highlights some theoretical review about training.

Definition:

According to (Becker, 1994), education and training are the most important contributors to human capital formation.In addition, According to (Dhar, 2015; Roger Buckley & Jim Caple, 1995)”the training can be defined as a planned and systematic effort to modify or develop knowledge, skill, and

attitude through learning experience, to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities”.

Following the study of (Bourouaha & Maliki, In press; Nazir et al., 2015; Salas & Cannon-Bowers, 2001),” Training is an essential component of industrial safety as it enhances the level of skills, comprehension, productivity, motivation, reliability, and commitment among the trainees”.The training is also one of a series of factors affecting organizational performance (Bee & Bee, 1994; Kaufman & Keller, 1994; Parry, 1996).

Starting from these different definitions and according to (Galia & Legros, 2004), the importance of the training strategy cannot be neglected because it represent from the important competitive advantages of the firm. Training motivation can be conceptualized as the direction, effort, intensity, and persistence that trainees apply to learning-oriented activities before, during, and after training (Ruth Kanfer, 1990; Tannenbaum & Yukl, 1992).

Training methods:

The training methods are specified following the goals in the future. According to (Hara, 2014; Lynch, 1992), they distinguish between three method of training that are:

OJT: on the job training:

This kind of training is invoked following (Albert et al., 2005) as one of the main mechanisms to promote the creation of internal labor markets. According to the studies of (Albert et al., 2005; Doeringer, 1971), “the on the job training provides workers with qualifications to make the properly

performance of their job tasks easy”. (Harris & Bonn, 2000; Ravichandran et al., 2015) found that on-the-job training was the most frequently applied method followed by Classroom instruction, Textbooks and manuals and Case studies and simulations.

Training tools that were used the most included texts and manuals followed by transparencies and flip charts, teleconferencing, computers, and audio-videotapes.

OFFJT: off the job training:

The Off the Job Training is the training method wherein the workers or employees learn their job roles away from the actual work floor. It comprises of a place specifically allotted for the training purpose that may be near to the actual workplace, where the workers are required to learn the skills and get well equipped with the tools and techniques that are to be used at the actual work floor.

Training as apprentice (apprenticeship)

The apprenticeship is cited from the ideal training method for the most participant following the study of (Ravichandran et al., 2015) to learn the necessary skills for the new employees.

Technology:

Technology is the new tools, infrastructure, materials, machines, that it is used in a sector in the aim of facilitating life. It is characterised with its growth and development through time, always new updates of technologies. Also, Technology is the effectiveness key of the administration

Dr. MaryFriend Shepard, coordinator of the Ph.D. Educational Technology Specialization in the Richard W. Riley College of Education and

Leadership at Walden University says “bringing technology tools into the classroom doesn't necessarily mean that teachers are leveraging them to develop students' 21st century skills...The key to integrating technology successfully is to convince teachers that they can do something with it that they can't do without it...if they're just transferring what they're already doing to online, then they'll balk — and for good reason. When they learn how powerful technology is, you can't stop them.(Delaney, 2011)

Technology as a form of engaging student learning, for example, is a strategy not limited to the online/virtual environment (Layne & Lake, 2014, p. 6).Technology remains a disruptiveinnovationand an expensive one(The Economist, 2008).For example, to bridge the gap between the physical separation of living and learning spaces, Elon university has developed living-learning communities and moved to increase the percentage of students living on campus (Prudence Layne, 2014, p. 27).

Fuelled by the great promise of computers and new technologies, higher education has made a large investment in electronics technology.Computer was used as a tool for administrative tasks, students review of material and not as an integral part of the student learning process (curriculum integration, presentation enhancement) (Mccannon & Crews, 2000, p. 119).

The increase in technological infrastructures is a direct result of the movement to increase revenue generated by distance education through online courses (Brown, 2003; Ertmer, 2005; Garrison & Kanuka, 2004; Katz, 1999; Schrum et al., 2005).“Technology allows students to become much more engaged in constructing their own knowledge, and cognitive

studies show that ability is key to learning success,” says New York City-based Queens College vice-president of institutional advancement, Susan Henderson (The Economist, 2008, p. 5)

Technology is enabling multi-model teaching, changing curricula and spawning rich forms of online research and collaboration. Following the technology widespread, more than 60% of the respondents of a study says that professors will soon teach in more than one medium in the same time (The Economist, 2008, p. 8).

To encourage the education and allow different student to benefit from the courses, the NYU's universities start using technology in education by integrating at least 3 cameras and sound mixer in every classes. The courses will be online in a period of 30 minutes, this latest facilitate to the student to access to the lessons in their free times.

Information and communication technologies ICT :

The ICT's are basing specially on using technological tools such as computer or laptops, smartphones, tablets or iPad ...etc. The ICT's contains all of: Hardwar, software and webs.

Hardwar: it englobes all of computers, smartphones,

Software: it represents the language used to use the previous tools (Hardwar)

Web: the space where we used tools and apply or execute the language. The web facilitates using the Hardwar and making it connected. This latest

ICTs can provide benefits such as reducing travel, saving time, and extending the geography of human community. They may replace valuable

human contact with a much less rewarding form of communication, fostering social isolation, or permit communication among people who might never have an opportunity to meet face to face. Tele-access encompasses all these substitutions, enhancements, and much more, by highlighting how people make social and technical choices about ICTs in ways that will reshuffle society, influencing who's in and who's left out.

Most ICT providers now prioritize choices that reduce long-term, negative environmental impact instead of just reducing operational costs. Over a computing system's lifetime, the array of costs includes design, verification, manufacturing, deployment, operation, maintenance, retirement, disposal, and recycling (Goel et al., 2012). It is worth emphasizing that ICT activity may cause radical change in the teacher's activity as well as in that of the student. However, the real evolution lies in the change of educational culture: a culture of collaborative learning, seeking to overcome the individualistic matrix through social action, whether it be from the perspective of interaction or representation (Silva et al., 2013). The role of ICT in education is becoming more and more important and this importance will continue to grow and develop in the 21st century. The continued use and development of ICTs within education will have a strong impact on the following points that are (Oliver, 2003):

- What is learned;
- How it is learned;
- When and where learning takes place and at least
- Who is learning and who is teaching.

Social-network:

Social-networking tools are helping to build connections with alumni and support career service activities (The Economist, 2008, p. 5). The

proliferation of new technologies (such as Facebook, Twitter, cloud computing, Google+, Skype, iPad, and smartphone apps) has not only transformed the way we deliver, interact with, and store digital information, but it has also created new opportunities for learning and its assessment. (Kulchitsky et al., 2014, p. 181).

Technology literacy:

Technology literacy's earliest official definition comes from the U.S. Department of Education, "computer skills and the ability to use computers and other technology to improve learning, productivity, and performance [technology literacy] has become as fundamental to a person's ability to navigate through society as traditional skills like reading, writing, and arithmetic" (1996, par.1).

According to (L et al., 2004, p. 7), "technological literacy means that an individual should have the capacity to "design, develop, control, use and assess technological systems and processes". The more necessary, it is not the effectiveness of technology, but the teacher's perception of the effectiveness of technology that determines whether technology will be used (Zhao & Cziko, 2001, p. 21).

According to (Spotts, 1999), there three levels of technology users that are:

High level users: they perceive greater benefits in using instructional technologies than low level users. High level users are the individuals who interest in technology and technology use. We find in this level researchers, teachers and faculty members and student with high skills.

Medium level users: medium users frequently referred to students or individuals that does not give big interest to the technology. We find in this level the students with low skills.

Low level users: low levels users are individuals that does not give any interest in technology.

Technology training:

The inexistence of technology training for teachers remains as one of the barriers of using technology in the SLP (Hoffman, 1997). As computer use continues to increase in the society, educators must also prepare for the use of computer in the SLP (student learning process) within the classroom (McCannon & Crews, 2000, p. 111)

According to (Spotts, 1999), if faculty are required to use technology, then faculty should receive technological support and academic recognition (promotion and tenure considerations). Other factors required for the successful incorporation of technology into pedagogy include time and training. One of the keys to understanding technology training might be that instructors prefer technology training that successfully integrates their pedagogy, not technology training that simply reveals how the instructional technology tools work (Georgina, 2007).

According to (Massy & Zemsky, 1995, p. 11-12), two general propositions surface when first considering an IT (information technology) conversion: It offers economies of scale, and mass customization. The faculty will learn to use the system(s) to accommodate their instructional needs. technology alone may do nothing to enable the integration of technology-based pedagogies.

The primary task of technology infrastructure is to support both instructional technology and student learning technology. This includes technology to enhance and support communication between student and instructors. Learning-support technology goals consist of creating communities (Olapiriyakul & Scher, 2006, p. 295).

This technology may create an online community that assists the self-acquisition of knowledge and enables students to share common values, expertise, and understanding multi-user software, online student help, and course tutorials (Georgina, 2007, p. 25). One must differentiate the kind of skills training that comes from learning a new technology or application from the kind of higher order skills that can be derived from higher education where we teach the person who saw the need and learned the requisite skills to create the technology or application to improve the human condition and way of life (Prudence Layne, 2014, p. 28).

Technology in higher education:

The role of technology in higher learning is to enhance human thinking and to augment the educational process, not to reduce it to a set of procedures for content delivery, control, and assessment (Popenici & Kerr, 2017).

Higher Education has seen a rapid increase in students who do not fit the traditional profile of a HE student. These students are commonly referred to as 'non-traditional students' (NTS), and are in general characterised by: their lower socio-economic background, being the first person from their families to enter HE, their academic under-preparedness;

their mature age and thus their juggling of work, family and academic responsibilities (Veronica Barnes et al., 2014, p. 47)

COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning), is a program that began in 2006 as a faculty-led initiative by Jon Rubin from the State University of New York (SUNY), in Purchase, NY, to support the development of collaborative online international courses (Hammonds & Oritsejafor, 2014, p. 145).

A globally networked learning environment (GNLE) refers to an environment for learning where students and faculty connect and engage in different parts of the world. The course objectives in GNLEs focuses on students gaining reflective learning and collaborative knowledge creation skills. The goal is that attaining these skills engenders global awareness and understanding of the participants' cultures. (Hammonds & Oritsejafor, 2014, p. 147).

From the transformational benefits that universities are embracing are distance education using technology and SLMS (sophisticated learning-management systems) (The Economist, 2008). Faculty members used to teaching in one way may be loath to invest the time to learn new methods, and may lack the budget for needed support (The Economist, 2008).

From the findings of the study (The Economist, 2008):

Technology has had and will continue to have significant impact on higher education. 63% of the survey respondents from all of private and public sectors declare that technological innovation will have a major influence on teaching methodologies over the next years.

Online learning is gaining a firm foothold in universities around the world. More than 66% of respondents from academia state that their institutions offer online courses.

Corporate-academic partnerships will form an increasing part of the university experience, at a time when locating funding and controlling costs are key concerns, and when only one-quarter of university chief information officers (CIOs) have a place at the table when it comes to setting strategy.

University respondents view technology as having a largely positive impact on their campuses, but acknowledge that operational challenges may hinder the full benefits from being realised (for example, tenure, promotions and other organisational practices may need adjustment to encourage faculty members to adopt new technologies).

Teacher technology training:

Comparing between teacher and trainer, Teachers may feel that their trainers are not as interested in the pedagogical effects of the technical tools. The perception is that the trainers have different goals than the teachers—focusing upon technology rather than pedagogy. Current research clearly states that the most effective training occurs when it incorporates peer to peer training, manifesting in shared ideas and practices among faculty (Brown, 2003; Curran, 2004; Ertmer, 2005; Mayo et al., 2005).

According to (Schrum, 1999), there are four points relating to teacher technology:

one, it takes considerably longer to learn about technology for personal or pedagogical use than learning a new teaching model; two, access to the new technology at school and at home is essential; three, fear of the

unknown must be addressed; four, the use of new technology may require teachers to reconceptualize the ways in which they teach. The necessity of the teacher technology training is to train teachers how to implement computers and technology in the educational setting (SLP) by teaching basic computer concepts and providing hands-on computer experience (Barker, 1994).

Following the importance of learning new technologies and using technology in the SLP , different Texas universities encourage their teachers to purchase laptop computers to reinforce the importance of computers in lesson planning and instruction (Smith et al., 1995). From the results (benefits) of teacher technology training:

Improve the quality of the courses for the students,

Improve the knowledge capacity of the student through integrating them in the SLP,

Create the innovation ability in the both teacher and students through using high technologies,

Improve the decision quality in both professional and academic fields,

Ensure the transfer of new technology to the students,

Ensure the ability to innovate because the teacher has packages of knowledge in addition to technology training, the teacher will have a big ability to transform or develop the previous knowledge to innovative ideas.

Improve the chance of getting feedback from the firms (selling innovative ideas)

Other innovations in education:

In the field of education and higher education, different methods are used to enhance and innovate the processes of teaching, here some of the most important ones:

Online-collaboration tools, software that supports individually paced learning, and learning-management systems are among the communications technologies most expected to improve academics over the next years.

Sophisticated learning-management systems and enhanced video and presentation tools are among other innovations that respondents say are likely to have a profound effect on the academic experience.

Online gaming and simulation software are cited by higher education and corporate respondents of a study as an innovation likely to be adopted among universities over the next years.

MOOC: massive open online courses

CAI: computer aided instruction: method of knowledge accumulation. It is the equivalent to lecturing from ages-old notes without regard for the student audience (and without regard for their circumstance or the culture in which they live when outside the classroom) (Morris & Stommel, 2014, p. 170).

Artificial intelligence:

The fast pace of technology innovation and the associated job displacement, acknowledged widely by experts in the field (source), implies that teaching in higher education requires a reconsideration of teachers' role and pedagogies. The current use of technological solutions such as 'learning management systems' or IT solutions push the universities to focus all their efforts on using technology in all sectors.

Artificial intelligence is defined as computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction and use of data for complex processing tasks (Popenici & Kerr, 2017).

Artificial intelligence is currently progressing at an accelerated pace, and this already impacts on the profound nature of services within higher education. The artificial intelligence opens a new horizon of possibilities for teaching and learning in higher education. With the rise of Artificial Intelligence solutions, it is increasingly important for educational institutions to stay alert and see if the power of control over hidden algorithms that run them is not monopolized by tech-lords.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is now enhancing tools and instruments used day by day in cities and campuses around the world. From Internet search engines, smartphone features and apps, to public transport and household appliances. Also, Assistive technologies—such as text to speech, speech to text, zoom capacity, predictive text, spell checkers, and search engines—are just some examples of technologies initially designed to assist people with a disability.

Challenges:

Many challenges are facing the sector of high education in our country, here some challenges that we have to look for them:

Many people find that online courses are a supplement to face-to-face classes,

Many people find that traditional degrees carry greater credibility than the degree earned online,

Insufficient resources in all fields,
Lack of adequate instructional design staff,
Lack of technological support issues,
Lack of suitable infrastructures,

Inside the classroom, technology may be a disruptive innovation in ways not intended. Survey participants along with those interviewed notes that pervasive multi-tasking between laptop, smartphone and other technologies in the classroom often distracts students. Lieutenant Colonel Greg Conti, director of West Point's Information Technology Operations Centre, says "it is impossible to sit someone in front of the world wide web and expect them not to use it. We, as faculty, teachers and administrators, have to recognise that if we're going to use technology in the classroom, we must find additional ways to keep content meaningful, even if it comes down to the simple task of requesting computer monitors down during the instructional period and back up during the hands-on portion of class." (The Economist, 2008, p. 14)

Conclusion and recommendations for the higher education:

The aim of this paper is to assess the important role of technology in high education to survive among highest high education institutes in the world. Following the changes in the world, training is appearing as one of the important sources of learning. Learning is the source of getting information that lead us to knowledge. Through applying the new knowledge in the main places, it will generate us the sustainability, this latest generate both or innovation and growth. However, with the execution of technology in all this steps, it will accelerate the process. In the last of this paper, here

are some recommendations proposed for the Algerian universities and administrations to survive:

Make facilities for the Algerian teachers to have computer and technological tools

Offering special formal training for teaching in the way of earning how to use technological tools in the SLP

Administrators should reward teachers who participate in this type of formal training with financial incentives and opportunities for more professional development.

Preparing spaces for special high technological training for teachers

Create spaces for the researchers (teachers, student) to develop new technologies following the characteristics of our societies that serve the science and the human

Launch coordination with high technological firms around the world to catch up the technological development

Give the priority to teachers to benefice from reduction the in the internet offers

Create special offers for teacher in all ICT (having technological tools, high internet offers, special types of smartphones, access to special high tech institutes)

Offering paid high technological training for teachers in developed states

The creation of virtual spaces for teachers to share, discuss and develop their competencies

Using digital technology in all levels (administration and academic)

Enhancing the use of artificial technology in the higher studies

Creation of rewarded competitions between teachers and administration in the aim enhancing them to use technology in all their activities

Enhancing student and teachers to innovate in the field of ICTs

Eliminate the barriers between teachers and administration through using technology,

To get better results, it is necessary to allow the students to develop all what do they learn in the aim of pushing them to innovation, especially by using ICT because it is the stage of creativity.

Accept and incubate the ideas and the imaginations of student because it could lead the world to a new era of technology

Enhancing the teacher to use technological tools allow the universities to create databases of all types of courses such as documents, videos, applications and others.

The integration of artificial intelligence in all fields following its importance in the new era of teaching and learning in high education.

Main references:

Albert, C., García-Serrano, C., & Hernanz, V. (2005). Firm-provided training and temporary contracts. *Spanish Economic Review*, 7(1), 67-88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10108-004-0087-1>

Amara, N., Landry, R., Becheikh, N., & Ouimet, M. (2008). Learning and novelty of innovation in established manufacturing SMEs. *Technovation*, 28(7), 450-463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2008.02.001>

- Anderson, T., & Whitelock, D. (2004). The Educational Semantic Web : Visioning and Practicing the Future of Education. <https://auspace.athabasca.ca/handle/2149/724>
- Barker, F. G. (1994). Integrating Computer Usage in the Classroom Curriculum through Teacher Training.
- Becker, G. S. (1994). Human Capital : A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education, 3rd Edition (Third Edition edition). University of Chicago Press. <http://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/H/bo3684031.html>
- Bee, R., & Bee, F. (1994). Training Needs Analysis and Evaluation. Chartered Institute of Personnel & Development.
- Beydoun, G., Kultchitsky, R., & Manasseh, G. (2007). Evolving semantic web with social navigation. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 32(2), 265-276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2005.11.035>
- Bourouaha, A., & Maliki, S. B. E. (In press). Determinants of Firms Innovation and the role of R&D Investment and Training : An Empirical evidence from Tunisian SME's. *International Journal of Business Innovation and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIR.2020.10026171>
- Brookfield, S. D. (2003). A critical theory perspective on accelerated learning. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 2003(97), 73-82. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.90>
- Brown, D. G. (Éd.). (2003). Developing Faculty to Use Technology : Programs and Strategies to Enhance Teaching. <https://www.amazon.com/Developing-Faculty-Use-Technology->

Strategies/dp/1882982622/ref=sr_1_1?dchild=1&keywords=978-

1882982622&qid=1599570474&sr=8-1

Chandy, R. K., & Tellis, G. J. (1998). Organizing for Radical Product Innovation : The Overlooked Role of Willingness to Cannibalize. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 35(4), 474-487. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3152166>

Curran, C. (2004). Strategies for E-Learning in Universities. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/78280303>

Darroch, J., & McNaughton, R. (2002). Examining the link between knowledge management practices and types of innovation. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 3(3), 210-222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930210435570>

Delaney, M. (2011). Training Teachers to Integrate Technology [Magazines]. *Technology Solutions That Drive Education*. <https://edtechmagazine.com/k12/article/2011/11/training-teachers-integrate-technology>

Dey, E. L., Burn, H. E., & Gerdes, D. (2009). Bringing the Classroom to the Web : Effects of Using New Technologies to Capture and Deliver Lectures. *Research in Higher Education*, 50(4), 377-393. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-009-9124-0>

Dhar, R. L. (2015). Service quality and the training of employees : The mediating role of organizational commitment. *Tourism Management*, 46, 419-430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.08.001>

Doeringer, P. B. ; P., Michael M. E. (1971). *Internal Labor Markets and Manpower Analysis* (1st edition). Heath Lexington Books.

- Ertmer, P. A. (2005). Teacher pedagogical beliefs : The final frontier in our quest for technology integration? *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 53(4), 25-39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02504683>
- Ferreira, M. J. M. (2012). Intelligent classrooms and smart software : Teaching and learning in today's university. *Education and Information Technologies*, 17(1), 3-25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-010-9134-8>
- Freel, M. S. (2005). Perceived Environmental Uncertainty and Innovation in Small Firms. *Small Business Economics*, 25(1), 49-64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-005-4257-9>
- Freeman, C. (1995). The 'National System of Innovation' in historical perspective. *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 19(1), 5-24.
- Galia, F., & Legros, D. (2004). Research and Development, Innovation, Training, Quality and Profitability : Evidence from France (SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 633973). Social Science Research Network. <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=633973>
- Garnham, C., & Kaleta, R. (2006). Introduction to hybrid courses. Teaching with Technology Today. University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee. <https://hccelearning.files.wordpress.com/2010/09/introduction-to-hybrid-course1.pdf>
- Garrison, D. R., & Kanuka, H. (2004). Blended learning : Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 7(2), 95-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2004.02.001>
- Gatignon, H., & Xuereb, J.-M. (1997). Strategic Orientation of the Firm and New Product Performance. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34(1), 77-90. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3152066>

Geoghegan, W. (1994). Stuck at the barricades : Can information technology really enter the mainstream of teaching an learning. AAHE Bulletin, 47(1), 13-16.

Georgina, D. A. (2007). Integration of technology in higher education pedagogy (p. 1-129) [The University of North Dakota]. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/116861/>

Germain, R. (1996). The role of context and structure in radical and incremental logistics innovation adoption. Journal of Business Research, 35(2), 117-127. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(95\)00053-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(95)00053-4)

Gilbert, S. W. (1994). If It Takes 40 or 50 Years, Can We Still Call It a Revolution? Educational Record, 75(3), 19-28.

Goel, B., McKee, S. A., & Sjalander, M. (2012). Techniques to Measure, Model, and Manage Power. In A. Hurson & A. Memon (Éds.), Advances in Computers (Vol. 87, p. 7-54). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-396528-8.00002-X>

Hammonds, L. Z. H., & Oritsejafor, E. (Éds.). (2014). Navigating the Performance Arts in a Globally Networked Classroom. In Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries (2015 edition, p. 145-166). Springer.

Hara, H. (2014). The impact of firm-provided training on productivity, wages, and transition to regular employment for workers in flexible arrangements. Journal of the Japanese and International Economies, 34, 336-359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjie.2014.10.002>

- Harris, K. J., & Bonn, M. A. (2000). Training Techniques and Tools : Evidence from the Foodservice Industry. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 24(3), 320-335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109634800002400302>
- Hilsdon, J. (2010). What is learning development. In *Learning Development in Higher Education*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://www.amazon.com/Learning-Development-Education-Universities-Century/dp/0230241484>
- Hoffman, B. (1997). Integrating technology into schools. *The education digest*, 62(5), 51-51.
- Inzelt, A. (1996). Institutional support for technological improvement—The case of Hungary. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 51(1), 65-93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1625\(95\)00076-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-1625(95)00076-3)
- John T. Baun (Éd.). (2014). *Concentrated Learning : A Linear Approach to Knowledge for Higher Education*. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries (2015 edition)*. Springer.
- Katz, R. N. (1999). *Dancing with the Devil : Information Technology and the New Competition in Higher Education*. Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series. Jossey-Bass Publishers, 350 Sansome St.
- Kaufman, R., & Keller, J. M. (1994). Levels of evaluation : Beyond Kirkpatrick. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 5(4), 371-380. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.3920050408>
- Kim, R. Y. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on consumers : Preparing for digital sales. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.1109/EMR.2020.2990115>

- Koberg, C. S., Detienne, D. R., & Heppard, K. A. (2003). An empirical test of environmental, organizational, and process factors affecting incremental and radical innovation. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 14(1), 21-45. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1047-8310\(03\)00003-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1047-8310(03)00003-8)
- Kulchitsky, D. R., Amir F. Zeid, & Ahmed M. Hamza (Éds.). (2014). The Efficacy of LSA (Variant)-Based Feedback for Assessing Student Learning in an Introductory International Relations Course. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition, p. 181-194). Springer.
- L, S., Ray, Ryan, B., & A., W. S. (2004). Using Concepts and Theoretical Models to Support the Standards for Technological Literacy. *Technology teacher*, 63(5). <https://search.proquest.com/openview/d56c56a694571178ebe13867c0aeb1a4/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=34845>
- Layne, P. C., & Lake, P. (Éds.). (2014). *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition). Springer.
- Lee, J. (1995). Small firms' innovation in two technological settings. *Research Policy*, 24(3), 391-401. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333\(93\)00772-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333(93)00772-L)
- Lee, N., & Horsfall, B. (2010). Accelerated Learning : A Study of Faculty and Student Experiences. *Innovative Higher Education*, 35(3), 191-202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-010-9141-0>
- Lynch, L. M. (1992). Private-Sector Training and the Earnings of Young Workers. *The American Economic Review*, 82(1), 299-312.

- Massimiliano Brat, & Giulia Felice. (2012). Buyer-supplier relationships, internationalisation and product innovation (EFIGE Working Paper No 54; EUROPEAN FIRMS IN A GLOBAL ECONOMY, p. 1-36). BRUEGEL. http://bruegel.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/efige_wp54_2308121.pdf
- Massy, W. F., & Zemsky, R. (1995). Using Information Technology to Enhance Academic Productivity. Monograph. <https://www.educause.edu/ir/library/html/nli0004.html>
- Mayo, N. B., Kajs, L. T., & Tanguma, J. (2005). Longitudinal Study of Technology Training to Prepare Future Teachers. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 29(1), 3-15.
- Mccannon, M., & Crews, T. B. (2000). Assessing the Technology Training Needs of Elementary School Teachers. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 8(2), 111-121.
- Morris, S. M., & Stommel, J. (Éds.). (2014). The Course as Container : Distributed Learning and the MOOC. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition, p. 167-180). Springer.
- Nazir, S., Sorensen, L. J., Øvergård, K. I., & Manca, D. (2015). Impact of training methods on Distributed Situation Awareness of industrial operators. *Safety Science*, 73, 136-145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2014.11.015>
- Olapiriyakul, K., & Scher, J. M. (2006). A guide to establishing hybrid learning courses : Employing information technology to create a new learning experience, and a case study. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 9(4), 287-301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2006.08.001>

- Oliver, R. (2003). The role of ICT in higher education for the 21st century : ICT as a change agent for education. Proceedings of the Higher Education for the 21st Century Conference, Curtin. proceedings of the Higher Education for the 21st Century Conference, Curtin. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.83.9509&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Parry, S. B. (1996). Measuring Training's ROI. *Training and Development*, 50(5), 72-77.
- Popenici, S. A. D., & Kerr, S. (2017). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-017-0062-8>
- Prince, M. (2004). Does Active Learning Work? A Review of the Research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223-231. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2004.tb00809.x>
- Prudence Layne (Éd.). (2014). *Transforming Higher Education Institutions : Higher Education : A Slow Route to Revolutionary Innovation*. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition). Springer.
- Ravichandran, S., Cichy, K. E., Powers, M., & Kirby, K. (2015). Exploring the training needs of older workers in the foodservice industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 44, 157-164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2014.10.003>
- Roger Buckley, & Jim Caple. (1995). *The theory and practice of training* (third edition).

- Romijn, H., & Albaladejo, M. (2002). Determinants of innovation capability in small electronics and software firms in southeast England. *Research Policy*, 31(7), 1053-1067. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(01\)00176-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(01)00176-7)
- Rosenberg. (1982). *Inside the Black Box : Technology and Economics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Royce Ann Collins (Éd.). (2014). What's an Instructor to Do? In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition, p. 221-235). Springer.
- Ruiter, G., & Johnson, C. (2003). *The Importance of Light and Colour When Designing Classrooms : (Re)Envisioning Classrooms*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Ruth Kanfer, P. L. A. (1990). Ability and Metacognitive Determinants of Skill Acquisition and Transfer. 91.
- Salas, E., & Cannon-Bowers, J. A. (2001). The science of training : A decade of progress. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 471-499.
- Schrum, L. (1999). Technology professional development for teachers. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 47(4), 83-90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02299599>
- Schrum, L., Burbank, M. D., Engle, J., Chambers, J. A., & Glassett, K. F. (2005). *Post-Secondary Educators' Professional Development : Investigation of an Online Approach to Enhancing Teaching and Learning*. *Internet and Higher Education*, 8(4), 279-289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2005.08.001>

- Scott, P. A. (2003). Attributes of high-quality intensive courses. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 2003(97), 29-38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.86>
- Silva, B. D. da, Gomes, M. J., Oliveira, L. R., & Blanco, E. (2013). The use of ICT in higher education : Work in progress at the University of Minho. *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*, 1-13.
- Smith, R. A., Houston, W. R., & Robin, B. R. (1995). Preparing preservice teachers to use technology in the classroom. *The Computing Teacher*, 22(4), 57-59.
- Spotts, T. H. (1999). Discriminating factors in faculty use of instructional technology in higher education. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 2(4), 92-99. JSTOR.
- Stover, W. J. (2007). Simulating the Cuban Missile Crisis : Crossing Time and Space in Virtual Reality. *International Studies Perspectives*, 8(1), 111-120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-3585.2007.00272.x>
- Strachan, R., & Liyanage, L. (Éds.). (2014). *Active Student Engagement : The Heart of Effective Learning*. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition, p. 255-274). Springer.
- Subramaniam, M., & Youndt, M. A. (2005). The Influence of Intellectual Capital on the Types of Innovative Capabilities. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(3), 450-463. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2005.17407911>
- Tannenbaum, S. I., & Yukl, G. (1992). Training and Development in Work Organizations. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 43(1), 399-441. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ps.43.020192.002151>

- Tether, B. S. (2002). Knowledge and Investment : The Sources of Innovation in Industry: Rinaldo Evangelista, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, UK, and Northampton, MA, USA, 1999. *Research Policy*, 31(1), 183-184. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(00\)00156-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(00)00156-6)
- The Economist. (2008). The future of higher education : How technology will shape learning (The Economist, p. 1-31) [Newspaper]. <http://graphics.eiu.com/upload/the%20future%20of%20universities.pdf>
- Verma, S., & Gustafsson, A. (2020). Investigating the emerging COVID-19 research trends in the field of business and management : A bibliometric analysis approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 118, 253-261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.06.057>
- Veronica Barnes, Daniela Gachago, & Eunice Ivala (Éds.). (2014). Digital Storytelling in Industrial Design. In *Global Innovation of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education : Transgressing Boundaries* (2015 edition). Springer.
- Wes Cohen. (1995). Empirical Studies of Innovative Activity and Performance. In P. Stoneman (Éd.), *Handbook of the Economics of Innovation and Technological Change* (1 edition). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Wuyts, S., Dutta, S., & Stremersch, S. (2004). Portfolios of Interfirm Agreements in Technology-Intensive Markets : Consequences for Innovation and Profitability. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(2), 88-100. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.68.2.88.27787>
- Zhao, Y., & Cziko, G. A. (2001). Teacher Adoption of Technology : A Perceptual Control Theory Perspective. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 5-5.

